

A Practice-Based Case Study of a Structured Literacy Intervention for a Kindergarten Student Receiving Tier 3 MTSS Support

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Abstract

This practice-based case study investigates the effects of a Structured Literacy intervention integrating multisensory phonics on the early reading development of a five-year-old kindergarten student identified for Tier 3 MTSS support due to significant deficits in alphabet naming fluency (ANF) and first sound fluency (FSF).

Grounded in established research on Structured Literacy and multisensory phonics instruction, an individualized 10-session intervention was designed and implemented. The intervention consisted of an initial six-session phase delivered twice weekly, followed by a planned three-week interval to examine retention, and a subsequent four-session review phase. Instruction targeted letter-name automaticity and initial phoneme identification through explicit, systematic, and cumulative routines, incorporating articulatory cues, tactile materials, rhythm-based activities, and structured review.

Baseline assessments indicated substantial delays (ANF = 15; FSF = 0). Following the initial phase, the student demonstrated measurable gains (ANF = 22; FSF = 4), and by the end of the review phase, performance improved to ANF = 25 and FSF = 6. Although FSF remained below the kindergarten benchmark, qualitative data revealed meaningful changes in learning behavior, including increased independence, reduced reliance on teacher prompting, improved self-correction, and spontaneous use of articulatory strategies. The planned interval further confirmed partial retention of acquired skills, supporting the durability of the intervention effects.

To extend learning beyond the instructional setting, a family-oriented literacy guide was provided to support home-school continuity. These findings suggest that individualized, multisensory Structured Literacy interventions can effectively accelerate foundational reading development while also highlighting the importance of incorporating retention-focused designs and behavioral indicators in early literacy intervention research.

Keywords: Structured Literacy, Multisensory Phonics, Early Literacy, MTSS Tier 3, Case Study

1. Relevant Background Information

- **Student Name:** Zaya
- **Grade Level:** Kindergarten
- **Description of Student:**

a. Student Background and Home Context

Zaya is a five-year-old African American girl who attends kindergarten. She lives in a single-parent home with four siblings. Her mother works part-time and is very supportive of school communication, but the family has limited time and resources to help with learning at home. Zaya gets along well with her classmates, and her general classroom behavior is stable.

b. Learner Characteristics

English is her first language, but her early literacy skills are developing more slowly than her peers. She often watches her friends before trying reading tasks and shows low confidence during literacy activities. She is not yet able to do blending or segmenting, and she usually cannot produce the first sound on her own. When a new sound or word is introduced, she tends to stop and wait for the teacher's model. She feels more comfortable when instructions are short and clear, and she participates better with familiar routines.

c. Student Strengths

Zaya tries again when encouraged, even if she hesitates at first. She is very good at copying the teacher's mouth movements and gestures, which helps during phonics instruction. She focuses well during hands-on tasks like clay, cards, or sand trays. She also responds strongly to rhythm and songs, and her participation increases right away. She builds positive relationships with peers and works cooperatively during one-on-one support.

d. Areas of Need

She has difficulty matching alphabet letters with their sounds, and her phonemic awareness skills are still at an early stage. She cannot segment or blend sounds yet, and she often waits for the teacher instead of trying independently. Her confidence is low during reading tasks, and she tends to follow her friends rather than take the first step. She also struggles to remember skills without repeated practice.

e. Learning Preferences

Zaya learns best with visual supports and clear teacher modeling. Predictable routines help her stay calm and focused. She engages well in activities with music, rhythm, and hands-on materials, and these activities help her maintain attention for a longer time.

f. Emotional and Behavioral Profile

Zaya is sensitive to mistakes and can be quiet at first. However, she becomes more engaged when the environment feels warm and safe. She participates more actively in one-on-one settings, and small successes motivate her to continue working.

g. Key Observations During Early Sessions

When new sounds or words were introduced, she often stopped and looked to the teacher for help. She was not able to say the first sound independently and made little attempt to blend sounds together. She frequently watched her peers' mouth movements before trying herself. In contrast, she showed high energy and confidence during chant and song activities. Short, repeated scaffolds helped her answer correctly and stay engaged.

h. Implications for Instruction

Based on her strengths and needs, Zaya will benefit from explicit and step-by-step instruction, along with multisensory activities that connect sounds and letters. She needs predictable routines and many short, repeated practice opportunities. Warm feedback and quick reinforcement will help reduce her stress and build her confidence during reading tasks. Zaya has no formal disability diagnosis, but she receives Tier 3 MTSS support because she shows large gaps in early literacy skills. She does not have an IEP, but her classroom supports include repeated directions, visual cues, and step-by-step modeling during reading tasks.

2. Baseline Assessments

- **Assessment 1:**

- **Type of Assessment:** Alphabet Naming Fluency (ANF), First Sound Fluency (FSF)
- **Date Administered:** September 18, 2025 (Sample 1)
- **Results:**

a. ANF: Zaya was able to name 14 uppercase letters. She responded slowly, and she could recall only a few letters that were familiar to her. Most letters were hard for her to remember on her own.

b. FSF: Her score was 0. She could not say the first sound of the given words. Instead, she repeated the whole word or did not respond.

- **Observations:**

During both assessments, Zaya paused for a few seconds before answering. When she was unsure, she looked at the teacher's mouth or whispered quietly as if

checking her answer. Her automaticity with letter names was very low, and her phonemic awareness seemed to be at an early stage. She will need repeated and structured practice to build basic letter and sound skills.

- **Assessment 2:**

- **Type of Assessment:** Alphabet Naming Fluency (ANF), First Sound Fluency (FSF)
- **Date Administered:** September 19, 2025 (Sample 2)
- **Results:**

a. ANF: Zaya named 15 uppercase letters correctly. This was similar to the previous day (14 letters), so the baseline score was set at 15. She still showed slow responses and hesitated often.

b. FSF: Her score was again 0. She continued to repeat the whole word instead of saying just the first sound.

- **Observations:**

Zaya continued to wait for visual cues from the teacher. For example, when asked, “What is the first sound of man?”, she repeated “man” instead of saying /m/. This showed again that her phonemic awareness is still at a very early level. She will need multisensory and step-by-step support to improve this skill.

3. Summary of Baseline Assessments

The ANF and FSF assessments were administered in a quiet area of the classroom to reduce distractions. Zaya sat close to the teacher so she could hear each prompt clearly, and no accommodations were needed beyond providing simple and consistent directions. This ensured that the baseline data reflected her true skill level.

- **Baseline Graph:**

- **Analysis of Data:**

Zaya's baseline assessment results clearly show that she has a significant gap in her early literacy skills, particularly in letter knowledge and phonemic awareness. In the Alphabet Naming Fluency (ANF), Zaya correctly named 15 letters in one minute. This is 10 below the Kindergarten Fall benchmark of 25, placing her well below benchmark. Zaya's response time was slow, and her consistency was lacking. The issue is not just that she can't recall letters, but also the lack of automaticity in identifying them. During the assessment, Zaya often paused for a few seconds before answering, looking to the teacher or a peer for cues, and trying to mimic their mouth movements. These behaviors suggest that Zaya lacks automatic letter-name recognition, indicating the need for repeated and explicit instruction. I reviewed the baseline data together with the host teacher and the reading specialist, and we discussed patterns in Zaya's responses, including her hesitation, slow processing, and reliance on teacher cues.

In the First Sound Fluency (FSF) assessment, Zaya scored 0, indicating she struggles significantly with phoneme segmentation and phonemic awareness. A score of 0 means that she could not isolate or produce the first sound in any word independently. For example, when asked what the first sound in "man" was, she repeated the whole word "man" instead of saying /m/. This shows a lack of practice in phoneme isolation and blending skills. The 0 score from FSF shows that Zaya is well below benchmark in phonemic awareness, highlighting the urgent need for targeted intervention.

- **Conclusions:**

Zaya's baseline data shows a significant gap in both letter-name fluency and phonemic awareness, demonstrating a clear need for intensive intervention. Zaya requires Tier 3 intervention for both areas and needs structured, explicit support from the very basics.

- **Problem Identification:** Zaya lacks automaticity in letter-name recognition and has no phonemic awareness skills. The 0 score in FSF shows that her phonemic awareness is a major barrier to her learning.

- **Intervention Focus:** Zaya needs explicit and systematic instruction to build automaticity in letter-name recognition and to develop phoneme segmentation and blending skills. The goal is for Zaya to reach the benchmark level through repeated practice and small successes that build her confidence.

These results clearly show that Zaya needs Tier 3 support. Positive reinforcement and a warm, supportive environment will help increase her confidence and encourage active participation in reading tasks.

4. Student Goal for the Intervention Phase

- **Goal:**

The following goals were set to help Zaya build basic early literacy skills during the first six intervention sessions (three weeks). Based on the baseline results (ANF 15, FSF 0), I created simple and reachable first-step goalsto guide her early progress.

- **ANF Goal:** When Zaya is shown a randomized set of uppercase and lowercase letters, she will correctly name at least 20 letters within one minute by the end of six intervention sessions

- **FSF Goal:** When Zaya is given a teacher-read list of simple CVC words, she will say the first sound in at least 10 words within one minute by the end of six intervention sessions.

- **Method of Goal Setting:**

These goals were set as step-one goals toward the kindergarten fall benchmark (ANF 25, FSF 10). Zaya's baseline scores (ANF 15, FSF 0) showed a large gap from the benchmark, so I first set goals that she could realistically reach in the early stage.

I discussed the goals with the host teacher. Together, we considered Zaya's attention span, work stamina, and learning pace. We chose goals that she could meet within three weeks of instruction.

I also planned a three-week break after the six sessions. Then, I prepared four review sessions. This plan was made to check whether Zaya could keep her skills over time, not just remember them for a short period.

- **Rationale:** Zaya scored 0 on the First Sound Fluency test. This means she has not yet developed basic phonemic awareness.

The goal of 10 first sounds helps her learn the early steps: hearing sounds → separating sounds → saying the first sound.

Zaya also showed slow and unsure letter naming. Sometimes she waited for the teacher before answering. The goal of 20 letters helps her build automaticity and get ready for phonics. These first-step goals were designed to help Zaya feel successful early in the intervention. The break and review sessions were also planned to check whether she could retain what she had learned keep her learning. Overall, these goals match her current learning needs and support steady and realistic progress.

5. Research-based Individualized Intervention Plan

- **Chosen Intervention:** Structured Literacy Approach Using Multisensory Phonics

For this intervention, I chose a Structured Literacy approach with multisensory phonics. This method teaches sounds and letters in a clear and organized way. It is also known to be effective for students who struggle with phonological awareness and letter automaticity. This is why I felt it matched Zaya's current needs.

- **Research Citation:**

Moats, L. C. (2020). *Speech to print: Language essentials for teachers of reading*(3rd ed.). Brookes Publishing.

National Reading Panel. (2000). *Teaching children to read: An evidence-based assessment of the scientific research literature on reading and its implications for reading instruction*(NIH Pub. No. 00-4769). National Institute of Child Health and Human Development.

Research shows that Structured Literacy and Orton–Gillingham–based multisensory phonics help young learners improve phonological awareness, decoding skills, and automaticity.

- **Rationale:**

- **Target Skill Areas**

I focused on two skill areas:

- **Letter naming skills** (measured through ANF)

- **Initial Sound identification skills** (measured through FSF)

These skills were the weakest areas in Zaya's baseline results. They also match the Kindergarten Foundational Skills in phonological awareness and letter–sound correspondence.

- **Based on Student Needs**

In the baseline, Zaya could not identify initial sounds (FSF = 0). She also hesitated when naming letters and waited for prompts. This showed that her phonological awareness and automaticity were not yet developed. Zaya also stayed focused better when the activity was short, simple, and repeated.

Because of this, I felt that a Structured Literacy approach was the best fit. It teaches sounds and letters one step at a time. It builds skills slowly and clearly. It

also uses repetition and multisensory support, which helps students like Zaya stay engaged

- **Alignment with Curricular Standards**

This intervention supports the Kindergarten Foundational Reading Skills.

- **CCSS RF.K.2: Phonological Awareness**

- **CCSS RF.K.3: Letter–Sound Correspondence**

Since Zaya struggled in these exact areas, the SL approach aligned naturally with the curriculum. It also allowed me to teach these skills in small, manageable steps.

- **Strengths & Background**

Zaya enjoys visual materials and hands-on activities. She also participates very well in simple games and repeated tasks. Because of her strengths, multisensory instruction worked well. Activities like tracing letters in sand or shaking a rhythm instrument helped her stay focused and learn connections between letters and sounds. This is why the Structured Literacy + Multisensory approach fit her so well.

- **Intervention Details:**

- **Frequency:**

Two sessions per week for three weeks (6 sessions total), about 30 minutes each. After the initial intervention phase, I also conducted four review sessions over two weeks to check whether Zaya could maintain the skills over time

- **Duration:**

The intervention was delivered twice a week for three weeks, for a total of six sessions. Each session lasted about 30 minutes and included repeated and cumulative practice. After completing these first six sessions (Phase 1), I intentionally added a three-week break to check whether Zaya could retain the skills over time. Following the break, I provided four additional review sessions across two weeks (Phase 2), bringing the total intervention to ten sessions.

- **Materials Needed:**

Picture cards, sound cards, mouth-shape cards, sand tray, playdough, rhythm instruments, and teacher-made materials.

○ **Description:**

I used the core principles of Structured Literacy: **explicit, systematic, cumulative and multisensory instruction.**

▪ **Small, Sequential Sets**

I taught only three letters at a time (b–c–d → m–n–s → t–p–g). Before moving to a new set, we reviewed the previous one. This helped Zaya keep what she learned.

▪ **Explicit Instruction**

For each new letter:

- I modeled the correct sound.
- Zaya repeated it.
- She wrote the letter in sand or traced it with her finger.
- She matched letters with simple pictures.

This helped her build clear sound–letter connections.

▪ **Multisensory Instruction**

Each session included tactile, auditory, or movement-based activities.

Examples include:

- Sand tray writing
- “Letter Cafe” (ordering letters)
- Sound Detective Game
- Rhythm shaker activities

These helped Zaya stay engaged and remember what she learned.

▪ **Phonological Awareness Practice**

We practiced initial sound identification in every session.

Activities included:

- Sorting pictures by first sound
- Clapping when a target sound was heard

- Choosing the correct card after hearing a sound

This directly supported Zaya’s greatest area of need.

- **Cumulative Review**

Every session included review of previously learned letters. Near the end, we added short timed naming practice to build automaticity.

- **Curriculum & Material Adaptations:**

I adapted the curriculum and materials to match Zaya’s needs, strengths, and learning pace.

- **Shorter attention span:** Activities were kept to 3–5 minutes each.

- **Visual learner:** Used many picture cards, mouth-shape cues, and gestures.

- **Difficulty with sound discrimination:** Added clearer sound contrasts and articulatory cues.

- **Support for grade-level access:** Aligned tasks with RF.K.2 and RF.K.3 while keeping them small and manageable.

- **Preventing overload:** Limited the number of letters per session and increased review time.

- **Maintaining confidence:** Reduced difficulty when needed and increased challenge when skills improved.

After each session, I reflected on Zaya’s performance and adjusted the next lesson. These flexible adjustments helped her stay engaged and make steady growth.

6. Explicit Lesson Plans:

Intervention Lesson Plan

	Teaching Day 1	Teaching Day 2	Teaching Day 3
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Student Goal for the Intervention Phase:

With simple and hands-on phonics activities using letter cards and picture cards, Zaya will say the first sound in short, one-syllable words and tell the correct sound for the target letters /b, m, t, c, d, g/. She will do this with at least 70 percent accuracy and answer within five seconds by the end of the first three sessions. This goal fits her because she learns better with short, clear routines, and she stays motivated when she can use a simple strategy like touching her mouth shape before she answers. The goal matches the Kindergarten standards for phonological awareness and letter–sound skills (RF.K.2 and RF.K.3).

Chosen Research-Based Intervention (Citation required):

I selected a multisensory phonics intervention based on the Structured Literacy approach. Research shows that explicit and systematic phonics instruction improves phonological awareness and early decoding skills in young learners (Moats, 2020; National Reading Panel, 2000).

Daily Topic	Initial sound identification and LSC Set 1: /b/, /m/, /t/	Review and build automaticity with /b/, /m/, /t/	Learning Letter–Sound Correspondence(LSC) Set 2: /c/, /d/, /g/
Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Letter cards (B, M, T) - Picture cards (ball, mom, tap) - Sand tray - Mouth shape cards - Sound Detective activity sheet 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Letter cards (B, M, T) - Rhythm shaker - Role-play cards (menu, small food items) - Stopwatch 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Letter cards (C, D, G) - Picture cards (cat, dog, goat) - Playdough - Rhythm instruments (toy drum, shaker, or clapping patterns) - Colored mats or colored paper sections for sound sorting - Mouth shape cards for articulatory cues
IN Standard (s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - K.RF.2.1: Identify and produce the sounds associated with individual consonants. - K.RF.2.3: Blend and segment sounds in spoken one-syllable words. - K.RF.1.1: Recognize and name all upper- and lowercase letters. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - K.RF.2.1: Identify and produce the sounds associated with individual consonants. - K.RF.1.1: Recognize and name all upper- and lowercase letters. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - K.RF.2.1: Identify and produce the sounds associated with consonants. - K.RF.1.1: Recognize and name upper- and lowercase letters.
Objective	Student will be able to listen to the sounds /b/, /m/, and /t/ and choose the correct picture and say the sound with at least six out of nine correct responses by the end of the session, using letter cards and picture cards during structured phonics activities.	Student will be able to say the correct sounds for B, M, and T with at least 80 percent accuracy and respond within five seconds during the Letter Café activities.	Student will be able to identify the sounds /c/, /d/, and /g/ and match each to the correct picture with at least 70 percent accuracy during the picture–sound matching tasks.
Daily Assessment	During each activity, accuracy and response time are recorded on a simple data sheet, along with the number of opportunities Zaya has to respond (writing the letter, saying the sound, choosing the correct card).	During today’s lesson, I record Zaya’s accuracy when naming letters and identifying the first sound. I also note how quickly she responds and whether she uses the strategies modeled yesterday. I check whether	During today’s lesson, I record the student’s accuracy for the new sounds /c/, /d/, and /g/ and note whether she can match each picture to the correct sound. I also observe how often she checks for throat vibration

	<p>To check her understanding, brief think-aloud questions are used, such as “Why did you pick this card for /m/?” Throughout the lesson, I also observe whether she begins to use her own articulatory cues (for example, mentioning her lips or tongue when making a sound). At the end of the session, all notes are reviewed to identify error patterns that should be retaught on Day 2. Progress-monitoring for the skills introduced in Session 1 will take place on Day 2 using the same ANF/FSF assessment format.</p>	<p>she remembers /m/ and /b/ without prompts and if she still confuses /t/. I look for signs of independent strategy use, such as repeating the sound before choosing a card. At the end of the session, I compare today’s ANF and FSF scores with her baseline to see early growth. This session includes progress monitoring with ANF and FSF, which helps me understand how the intervention is supporting Zaya’s overall early literacy development, not just today’s skills. I use this information to adjust upcoming instruction. At the end of the day, I will briefly share these observations with the host teacher to plan small adjustments for tomorrow’s session.</p>	<p>to tell the difference between /d/ and /g/. During the playdough activity, I monitor how well she forms each letter and how long it takes her to complete the shape. I write down any error patterns, such as mixing /c/ and /d/ or needing repeated prompts, and use this information to decide what needs to be retaught during the next session. At the end of the lesson, I identify which sounds still require focused practice. Progress monitoring for these skills will take place on Day 4 using the same ANF and FSF procedures. I will also briefly share these observations with the host teacher so we can plan adjustments for Day 4.</p>
<p>Anticipatory Set</p>	<p>The teacher begins by connecting the lesson to something familiar. She compares the first letter of the student’s name, Zaya, with the sound in the word “blue” to help the student remember how beginning sounds work. The student practices making the /b/ sound by pressing her lips together and opening them, which activates her background knowledge about how sounds start. The teacher then gives a short warm-up by saying one sound at a time, such as /b/, /m/, or /t/, and the student shakes the rhythm shaker and chooses the matching letter card. The teacher uses the routine cue “Listen to the first sound” to check for understanding and notice</p>	<p>The teacher begins with a short review of the sound /t/ by showing the letter card and saying simple words like “tap,” “top,” and “turtle.” Each time the student hears the beginning sound, she shakes the rhythm shaker and holds up the /t/ card. This quick check helps the teacher see whether the student remembers the sound that was difficult on Day 1 and prepares her for today’s work. The teacher then shows small picture cards, such as a muffin, a ball, and a taco, and asks, “Which food begins with this sound?” The student listens for /m/, /b/, or /t/ and points to the matching picture. This fast reaction activity helps the student focus and gets her ready for</p>	<p>The teacher begins by reviewing the sounds from Day 2 using the B, M, and T cards. The student names each sound and gives one example word from the previous lesson. Because /t/ needed more practice, the teacher adds a short review with words like “tap” and “top” to help the student connect yesterday’s learning to today’s lesson. Next, the teacher shows picture cards such as a cat, dog, and goat and asks the student to guess the beginning sound. This helps the teacher see what the student already knows before introducing the new letters C, D, and G. To set a positive tone, the teacher says, “We will learn new sounds today, and</p>

	<p>any areas of confusion. To build a positive learning tone, the teacher reminds the student that it is okay to make mistakes and says, “We are sound detectives today.” This helps the student feel safe, engaged, and ready for the new lesson.</p>	<p>the Letter Café role-play. To build a positive tone, the teacher says, “You get to be the café owner again today. We will listen for the first sound and choose the right food. You worked hard yesterday, and even if the sounds feel tricky, we can figure them out together.” This message helps the student feel supported and confident as the lesson begins.</p>	<p>rhythm will help our ears listen carefully.” The teacher adds, “It is okay if the sounds feel tricky. We will practice together.” This helps the student feel supported and ready to learn. This warm-up also prepares her to notice the difference between voiced and unvoiced consonants, which is a key focus today.</p>
<p>Procedures</p>	<p>1) Explicit Teaching / Modeling (I Do) - Teacher models how to make /b/ by pressing lips together and releasing with voice. - Teacher uses a think-aloud: “I check my lips first and feel my voice.” - Teacher writes Bin the sand tray while saying /b/. - Teacher models correcting an error by comparing /b/ and /p/: “This one has air. This one has voice.” - Teacher briefly models /m/ and /t/, breaking them into small, simple steps.</p> <p>2) Guided Practice (We Do) Sound Detective Game Steps - Teacher says a word: “ball,” “mom,” “tap.” - Student and teacher say the first sound together.</p> <p>- Student writes the letter in the sand tray with support. - Student finds the matching picture card. - Teacher uses repeated cues: “Listen to the first sound,” “Say it as you write.” - Teacher checks</p>	<p>1) Explicit Teaching / Modeling (I Do) - The teacher shows the letters B, M, and T in random order and says each sound clearly. - The teacher models quick recall by responding within five seconds. - Think-aloud: “When I see the letter, I try to pull the sound from my brain right away. Yesterday’s practice helps my brain work faster today.” - The teacher explains what to do when the sound feels confusing: “If the sound does not come right away, I check how my mouth moves and try again.” - The teacher models a common error with /t/ and corrects it so the student can see how to fix mistakes.</p> <p>2) Guided Practice (We Do) (1) Letter Café Role-Play - The student plays the café owner, and the teacher plays the customer. - The teacher orders items by their first sound. Example: “I would like a /m/ muffin, please.” - The student listens for the</p>	<p>1) Explicit Teaching / Modeling (I Do) - The teacher models the target sound /d/ and shows how the tongue touches right behind the upper teeth. - The teacher explains the step: “My tongue touches first, and then my voice turns on.” - Think-aloud: “I picture where my tongue goes, and I check for the buzz in my throat.” - The teacher models a mistake and corrects it: “This one had no buzzing. That would sound like /c/. I will try again with my voice to make /d/.” - This model helps the student see how to check placement, voice use, and accuracy. - The teacher also emphasizes that feeling throat vibration is the key strategy for telling /d/ and /g/ apart.</p> <p>2) Guided Practice (We Do) (1) Playdough Letter Shaping - The teacher asks the student to make C, D, and G with playdough.</p>

<p>understanding: “What sound did you hear at the beginning?”</p> <p>3) Independent Practice (You Do)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teacher gives the student a new word and waits for independent response. - Student says the first sound without help. - Student picks the letter card and writes it in the sand tray. - Student finds the picture card on her own. - Teacher reminds: “Try it yourself first. I will help if you need it.” - Teacher observes accuracy, especially with /t/, to note error patterns. <p>4) Scaffolding Sequence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Verbal prompt: “Press your lips together first.” - Visual prompt: Mouth picture card, pointing to the letter. - Minimal prompt: Small gesture or eye contact. - Teacher fades prompts as student responds correctly. - If confusion continues, teacher slows the word or models again. <p>5) Feedback Types</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Task feedback: “Yes, that is the correct sound for ‘ball’.” - Process feedback: “You listened carefully and used the picture to help.” - Self-regulation feedback: “You kept trying, even after a mistake.” - Teacher uses theme-based motivation: “You are a strong sound detective.” 	<p>beginning sound, says the sound, and hands the correct picture card.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher repeats the sound with the student to check understanding. - The playful setting helps the student practice phonics in a natural way. - The teacher occasionally asks, “How did you know it was /m/? Tell me what you checked.” to help the student explain her thinking. - The student chooses whether to answer by saying the sound or by pointing to the correct picture card. This small choice gives her a sense of control and supports her motivation during the activity. <p>(2) Quick Sound Match (1-minute round)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A one-minute timer is used. - The teacher shows B, M, and T quickly, one at a time. - The student says the sound within five seconds for each card. - Before starting, the student chooses the first letter to build confidence and motivation. - The teacher notes accuracy and any letters that still need more support. <p>3) Independent Practice (You Do)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher shows the same letters again, but this time the student responds without help. - The student says the beginning sound and checks it by touching their mouth or looking at the letter card. - The student selects the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher reminds the student: “Say the sound while you make the letter.” - The activity connects movement, touch, sight, and sound so the student practices each phoneme in many ways. <p>(2) Sound Sorting with Rhythm</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher uses a simple drumbeat or clapping pattern to help with listening. - The teacher shows picture cards (cat, dog, goat). - The student sorts the cards into /c/, /d/, or /g/. - The rhythm helps the student stay focused and respond smoothly. - The student may choose whether to say the sound first or place the picture first, which gives her a sense of control and increases motivation. <p>3) Independent Practice (You Do)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher holds up the letters C, D, and G one at a time. - The student says the sound independently and checks accuracy by touching their throat or looking at the letter shape. - The student chooses the correct picture card without help. - The teacher encourages self-correction: “Try it once more. What do you notice in your throat?” - The teacher notes whether the student can now tell the difference between /d/ and /g/ without prompts. - This task directly checks
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	<p>- Student chooses the first mystery picture to increase motivation.</p>	<p>matching picture card independently.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If the student makes an error, the teacher gives a brief chance to self-correct before offering help. - The teacher watches for progress with /t/, since this sound was difficult on Day 1. <p>4) Scaffolding Sequence If the student hesitates, the teacher provides support in this order:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Verbal prompt: “Think about how your lips move for that sound.” - Visual prompt: show the mouth card or picture card. - Minimal prompt: small gesture, nod, or pointing. Prompts are removed quickly so the student can try independently again. The teacher adjusts the level of support based on the student’s performance. <p>5) Feedback Types</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Task feedback: “Yes, that is the correct sound for this letter.” - Process feedback: “You looked carefully at the letter before saying the sound. That helped your accuracy.” - Self-regulation feedback: “You slowed down, fixed your mistake, and tried again. That shows good control.” - Motivation feedback: “You were faster than yesterday. Your practice is helping your brain work stronger.” 	<p>whether the student can apply today’s target sounds independently.</p> <p>4) Scaffolding Sequence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tactile cue: “Put your hand on your throat. Do you feel the buzz?” - Verbal cue: “Your tongue touches first for /d/.” - Visual cue: brief look at the mouth placement card. - Minimal cue: small gesture or nod. The teacher fades prompts step by step as the student becomes more accurate. <p>5) Feedback Types</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Immediate corrective feedback: “Listen again. That sound did not use your voice. Try /d/ with the buzz.” - Specific positive feedback: “You used your voice at the right time. That made your /d/ clear.” - Process feedback: “You checked your throat before choosing. That shows careful thinking.” - Encouragement for self-monitoring: “You fixed your own mistake. That helps you learn faster.”
Closure	<p>1) Quick Review We will look at the three sound cards again and say each sound one more time. Let’s check /b/, /m/, and /t/</p>	<p>1) Quick Review</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher will show the three sound cards again: B, M, and T. - The student will say each 	<p>1) Quick Review</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher and student review the three new sounds by matching the pictures of cat, dog, and goat with their

	<p>together.</p> <p>2) Next Step “Tomorrow, we will try to find these sounds even faster. You were a great sound detective today.”</p> <p>3) Positive Feedback: “I really liked how you settled into our sound detective routine so quickly! That helped us learn so much. And I loved how you stayed focused and kept trying, even when the sounds felt tricky.”</p>	<p>sound and give one food example from the Letter Café activity. For example: “/m/... muffin.” - This helps the student connect today’s learning to the role-play activity.</p> <p>2) Next Step - “Tomorrow, we will add new sounds. We will also play a faster Café game, and you can choose the first item again.” - This prepares the student for Lesson 3 and builds confidence by giving predictable structure.</p> <p>3) Positive Feedback “I liked how you listened carefully and spoke like a real café owner today. You stayed focused, and that helped you say the sounds more clearly.”</p>	<p>beginning sounds. - This quick review helps the student confirm what she learned today. It also allows the teacher to check for any remaining confusion.</p> <p>2) Next Step - The teacher explains what will happen during the next lesson: “Next time we will review these sounds again using the drum, and we will play Sound Detective to make your ears even stronger.” - After the review, the teacher asks, “Which sound felt easiest today, and which one do you want to practice more?” to support metacognition. - The teacher uses the student’s response to plan the review order for Day 4.</p> <p>3) Positive Feedback “You learned three new sounds very quickly today, and that is a big step. You listened carefully and stayed focused. That effort helped you grow as a reader.”</p>
<p>Self-Reflection:</p>	<p>The student showed good confidence with the sounds /m/ and /b/, and she responded quickly when the teacher used a familiar routine. The structured activities helped her stay focused, and she appeared comfortable attempting each sound even when she was unsure. This was an encouraging start to the intervention. The sound /t/ was still confusing for the student. She identified it correctly about three out of nine times, and she had difficulty</p>	<p>The student was very motivated during the café role-play, and this helped her stay involved in every part of the lesson. Her engagement and effort stood out today. One area that still needs support is the sound /t/. She needed more time to respond, usually around eight seconds. Because /t/ and /d/ can feel similar for young learners, I should be careful about the sound combinations I introduce next. I will avoid putting similar unvoiced sounds</p>	<p>The student was highly engaged during the playdough activity. The multisensory approach helped her stay focused, and she genuinely seemed to enjoy shaping the letters while saying each sound. This part of the lesson supported both her attention and her confidence. She continued to mix up /c/ and /d/, and she often produced /d/ and /g/ without using her voice, which made them sound more like unvoiced consonants. These patterns showed me that she</p>

<p>noticing the “no voice” feature and the correct tongue placement. This suggests that /t/ is not yet stable in her developing sound system. The teacher also noticed that she hesitated longer when /t/ followed another consonant, which may indicate that she needs more explicit contrast practice.</p> <p>For Day 2, the teacher plans to begin with a short warm-up that focuses only on /t/ so the student can revisit the sound in a low-pressure way. The teacher also plans to adjust the order of activities so the student begins with sounds she already feels confident about before moving into more challenging contrasts. This approach should reduce cognitive load, support early success, and create a smoother transition into new learning.</p>	<p>together when I design Set 2 so she does not feel overloaded.</p> <p>For tomorrow, I plan to start with a short warm-up for /t/ again. This should help her feel more confident and strengthen the accuracy she is building. I hope this extra practice can close the small gap I noticed today. I will also share this observation with the host teacher so we can decide together whether the warm-up should include more contrast practice for /t/.</p>	<p>needs more explicit practice with feeling throat vibration and distinguishing between voiced and unvoiced sounds. For Day 4, I plan to begin with a short warm-up that highlights this distinction. I will introduce a simple cue, “Feel the buzz in your throat,” and give her several chances to try it before we move into the main activities. I also want her to start with a sound she feels most confident about. Beginning with something easier should lower the cognitive load, build early success, and help her approach the more challenging contrasts with greater ease.</p> <p>These observations will guide my instructional decisions for Day 4 and help ensure that the intervention continues to meet her needs. I will also share these patterns with the host teacher so we can plan the warm-up sequence together.</p>
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	Teaching Day 4	Teaching Day 5	Teaching Day 6
<p>Student Goal for the Intervention Phase:</p> <p>Using Zaya’s baseline scores and the kindergarten reading goals, I will teach her with short and hands-on phonics activities. We will use picture cards, letter cards, a sand tray, and simple mouth cues. Zaya will say the first sound in short CVC words and tell the correct sound for the letters b, m, t, c, d, and g with at least 70 percent accuracy and within five seconds by the end of the first three sessions. She learns better when activities are clear and predictable, so I will use small movement cues and simple mouth checks to help her feel confident and work more independently.</p>			
<p>Chosen Intervention:</p> <p>I selected a multisensory phonics intervention based on the Structured Literacy approach. Research shows that explicit and systematic phonics instruction improves phonological awareness and early decoding skills in young learners (Moats, 2020; National Reading Panel, 2000).</p>			

Daily Topic	Review /c/, /d/, /g/ and strengthen sound discrimination (focus on voiced vs. voiceless and articulatory awareness)	Learning the sounds /n/, /s/, and /p/ (using songs, movement, and simple cues)	Review of /b, m, t/ and build words that link sound to letter to meaning. Practice blending. Read the decodable text A Hat.
Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Letter cards (C, D, G) - Picture cards (cat, dog, goat) - Playdough - Mouth shape (articulation) cards - “Broken letter” cards prepared by the teacher - Timer and simple recording sheet for accuracy and notes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Letter cards: N, S, P - Picture cards: nose, snake, popcorn - Pop sound effect - Small “nose cue” visual - Alphabet mats or large floor letters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Magnetic letters b, m, t, p, a - Mystery Bag - Letter cards and picture cards - Whiteboard and markers - Mirror for articulation - Decodable text A Hat - Simple recording sheet for sound accuracy, word reading, and self correction
IN Standard (s).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - K.RF.2.1: Identify and produce the sounds associated with individual consonants. - K.RF.3.2: Demonstrate basic knowledge of letter–sound correspondence. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - K.RF.2.1: Identify and produce the sounds associated with individual consonants. - K.RF.3.2: Demonstrate basic knowledge of letter–sound correspondence. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - K.RF.2.1 Identify and produce consonant sounds - K.RF.3.2 Show basic knowledge of letter sound correspondence - K.RL.1.1 Ask and answer questions about details in a text
Objective	Student will be able to match the sounds /c/, /d/, and /g/ to the correct letter and picture with at least 80 percent accuracy during structured multisensory activities using letter cards, picture cards, and playdough by the end of today’s session.	Student will be able to match each target sound (/n/, /s/, /p/) to the correct letter and picture during a listening task with at least 6 out of 9 correct responses by the end of the session.	Student will be able to match the sounds /b/, /m/, and /t/ to the correct letters and read the CVC words pat, tap, and map with at least 80 percent accuracy using a simple blending routine.
Daily Assessment	During this lesson, I keep a simple tally of correct and incorrect responses for /c/, /d/, and /g/ while Zaya builds and fixes letters with playdough. I note each time she notices a “broken” letter and corrects the shape on her own, and each time she still needs a reminder, especially for /c/. I also watch whether she uses the voicing strategy when she is unsure, such as putting her hand on her throat	I observe accuracy for /n/, /s/, and /p/, and note whether music or movement helps her remember each sound. I check if she uses the “nose cue” for /n/ or if she needs reminders. I keep records of her response time and how long she stays focused during the more active parts of the lesson. I also look for confusion between /p/ and /b/. At the end of the lesson, I review the notes to decide	During Quick Sound Match, I count how many letters she names correctly and record her ANF score for the day. In the Mystery Bag activity, I count how many beginning sounds she identifies correctly and write her FSF score. I also note any error patterns, such as mixing /t/ and /d/ or hesitation with certain lowercase letters, and I write down how confident

	<p>to feel vibration. After the session, I review these notes and complete a short checklist (error patterns for /c/, use of self-correction, and use of tactile cues). Today also includes a brief ANF and FSF progress check, so I can see how much growth there has been since earlier sessions and decide which sounds to emphasize first and for longer on Day 5.</p>	<p>which sounds need more practice on Day 6. Progress monitoring for today's skills will take place on Day 6.</p>	<p>she seems when answering. At the end of the session, I compare today's scores with her baseline (ANF 15 → 22; FSF 0 → 4) to show her overall growth across the intervention. These results help me decide which sounds need more practice and how much support to give during the next lesson. I will also share these results with the host teacher so we can plan how to keep supporting these sounds during classroom reading and writing time.</p>
<p>Anticipatory Set</p>	<p>The teacher begins by briefly reviewing the Set 1 sounds (B, M, and T). The student names each sound and gives one example word from earlier lessons. The teacher then does a quick speed quiz using the cue "Listen to the first sound" to help the student warm up and remember what she already knows. After this review, the teacher introduces the new sounds /c/, /d/, and /g/ and uses simple cues like touching the throat to show how voicing feels. These cues help the student notice how the sounds are different and let the teacher see where she might still be confused. The teacher also uses a short playful correction prompt, such as "Is this /d/ or /g/? Try it again," to keep the activity light and help the student feel comfortable taking risks. This short warm-up gets the student engaged and ready for the main instruction.</p>	<p>The teacher begins with a short review of the sounds /b/, /m/, and /t/ by holding up each card and asking the student to say the sound quickly. This activates prior learning and lets the teacher check for any gaps before starting new sounds. Then, the teacher shows simple cues for today's targets: touching the nose for /n/, making a "snake arm" for /s/, and pressing the lips together for /p/. A playful question like "Is this the snake sound or the nose sound?" helps the student relax, smile, and pay attention. This warm-up creates a positive tone, checks understanding, and prepares the student for the new lesson.</p>	<p>To begin the lesson, I review the sounds /b/, /m/, and /t/ by holding up each card and asking her to say the sound right away. This helps her remember what we learned before and lets me check if anything is still confusing. I also use our routine cue, "Show me how your mouth makes this sound," so she can feel how the sound is made. After the quick review, I switch to a short reaction warm-up. I show a card and ask, "Do you feel air or no air?" so she can notice the difference between /t/ and /d/. When she makes a mistake, I gently say, "Try again. Do you feel the air this time?" to help her stay calm and willing to try. This short warm-up helps her focus, brings back what she already knows, and prepares her for blending sounds and reading simple CVC words in today's lesson.</p>

<p>Procedures</p>	<p>1) Explicit Teaching / Modeling (I Do)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher models the sounds /d/and /g/and shows where the tongue touches for each. - The teacher explains: “My tongue touches behind my upper teeth, and my voice buzzes. That makes /d/.” - Think-aloud: “I picture where my tongue goes first, then I check my throat to see if it is buzzing.” - The teacher shows a “broken D” that was drawn on purpose and fixes it while talking through the thinking: “This part is too open, so it looks like C. When I make it round, it becomes D.” - The teacher makes an error on purpose and corrects it out loud: <p>“My throat did not buzz. That sounded like /c/. I will try again and turn on my voice for /g/.”</p> <p>2) Guided Practice (We Do)</p> <p>(1) Playdough Letter Shaping and Fixing Broken Letters</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The student makes C, D, and Gwith playdough. - The teacher says, “Say the sound while you make the letter.” - The teacher gives the student “broken letters” made incorrectly on purpose. - The student fixes the shape and says a word that begins with the sound. <p>Example: “Dog starts with /d/.”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher gives clear feedback about both the sound and the letter shape. 	<p>1) Explicit Teaching / Modeling (I Do)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher models how to make each target sound: <p>/s/: “Pull your lips a little to the side and let the air move between your teeth. sss.”</p> <p>/p/: “Press your lips together and let the air pop out, like popcorn.”</p> <p>/n/: “Touch your nose and say nnn. You will feel a small vibration.”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher uses simple think-alouds: “I check where the air goes first. Each sound feels different in my mouth.” - The teacher also models a correction: “That one did not sound like /n/. I will touch my nose again and try it slowly.” <p>2) Guided Practice (We Do)</p> <p>(1) Sound Song Routine</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher and student sing “s s s, I see a snake”while moving their arms like a snake. - For /p/, the teacher shows popcorn pictures and plays a “pop” sound. They chant together: “pop, pop, popcorn!” - For /n/, the student touches her nose and says “nnn, nose”, and practices a few simple nose-related words. - These routines use music, movement, and repetition to help the student remember each sound. <p>(2) Popcorn Sound Game</p>	<p>1) Explicit Teaching / Modeling (I Do)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher writes b, m, ton the board. - The teacher models each sound clearly: <p>/b/: “My lips stay together and then pop open. /b/, /b/, ball.”</p> <p>/m/: “My lips stay closed. The sound goes through my nose. /m/, /m/, mom.”</p> <p>/t/: “My tongue taps behind my teeth. A little air comes out. /t/, /t/, top.”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher uses a mirror and says, “Watch your mouth—popping, humming, puffing.” - The teacher models a mistake on purpose: Points to t and says /d/. Then corrects: “There was no air. That was /d/. Let me try again—/t/. Now I feel the air.” - The teacher explains their thinking: “I listen for the air. I watch my mouth. I check again.” (This supports the think-aloud strategy.) <p>2) Guided Practice (We Do)</p> <p>(1) Sound Match on the Board</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher says a sound and the student points to the matching magnetic letter. - If she hesitates, the teacher uses simple cues: “What do your lips do? Do you feel the air?”
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<p>(2) Sound Sorting with Rhythm</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher sets three areas for /c/, /d/, and /g/. - The teacher shows picture cards (cat, dog, goat). - The student places each card in the correct area while saying the first sound. - The teacher taps a simple rhythm to help the student stay focused and keep a steady pace. <p>3) Independent Practice (You Do)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher holds up the letters C, D, and G in random order. - The student says each sound on her own and checks accuracy by touching her throat or looking at the letter shape. - The student chooses the correct picture card without help. - If the student makes a mistake, the teacher encourages self-correction: "Try it again. What do you notice in your throat?" - The teacher notes whether the student can now separate /d/ and /g/ without prompts. <p>4) Scaffolding Sequence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Verbal cue: "Touch your throat. Do you feel the buzz?" - Visual cue: quick look at the mouth card or the simple tongue diagram. - Tactile cue: the teacher touches their own throat and asks the student to try. - Minimal cue: small nod or gesture. <p>The teacher fades the cues step by step as the student becomes more confident and</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Letter and picture cards for /n/, /s/, and /p/ are placed face-down. - The student flips a card, says the first sound, and runs to touch the matching floor letter. - The teacher supports her thinking by saying things like: "You used the song to remember /s/. That was smart." - "Closing your lips helped you make a stronger /p/ sound." <p>3) Independent Practice (You Do)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher gives one sound at a time without cues. - The student: Says the sound on her own, Picks the matching letter card, And places it next to the correct picture. - The student uses strategies she learned earlier, such as touching her nose for /n/ or checking lip position for /p/. - The teacher observes how often she can do this independently and notes any sounds she still mixes up. <p>4) Scaffolding Sequence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Verbal prompt: "Try touching your nose for /n/." - Visual prompt: Quick look at the nose picture or snake card. - Tactile prompt: Teacher touches their own nose or lips to model the cue. - Minimal prompt: Small gesture, nod, or smile. - The teacher fades prompts quickly as the student becomes more confident. 	<p>(2) Mystery Bag Game</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher shakes a small bag with magnetic letters. - The teacher says a sound; the student pulls out the matching letter. - Student holds it up, says the sound, and puts it on the board. - Teacher gives quick feedback: "Yes! That is the popping /b/ sound." - "Great humming /m/ sound." - "Good job feeling the air for /t/." <p>(3) Sorting and Fixing Mistakes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher mixes letters on purpose (ex: puts d next to t). - The student fixes the mix-up and explains how she knows. - Teacher prompts: "Feel the air. Which one is /t/? Which one is /d/?" <p>(4) Shared Word Building</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher builds pat, tap, map with magnetic letters. - The teacher models blending slowly: "p – a – t... pat." - The student helps blend the next words. <p>3) Independent Practice (You Do)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The student builds pat, tap, map on her own with magnetic letters.
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	<p>accurate.</p> <p>5) Feedback Types</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Task feedback: “You made the correct sound for dog. That was /d/.” - Process feedback: “You checked your throat before answering. That helped you choose the right sound.” - Self-regulation feedback: “You did not give up. You fixed it on your own.” - Motivation feedback: “You are getting better at hearing the difference. Your practice is working.” 	<p>5) Feedback Types</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Task feedback: “Yes, that was the correct sound for popcorn.” - Process feedback: “You listened carefully and used the movement to help you.” - Self-regulation feedback: “You kept trying even when the sound felt new.” - Motivation feedback: “Your sounds are getting clearer every time you practice. Nice work.” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - She points to each letter, says the sounds, and blends. - If she makes an error, the teacher waits for self-correction. - If needed, the teacher gives the smallest cue: “What do you feel? Try again.” - The teacher notes accuracy and types of support needed <p>4) Scaffolding Sequence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Verbal cue: “Check your air.” - Mirror cue: student looks at mouth shape. - Tactile cue: hand to feel airflow. - Visual cue: mouth cards. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Modeling: slow, clear sound demonstration. - Minimal cue: small nod or gesture. <p>Scaffolds are reduced as the student becomes more confident and accurate.</p> <p>5) Feedback Types</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Task feedback: “Yes, that is the right sound for b.” - Process feedback: “You checked the mirror first. That helped you.” - Self regulation feedback: “You fixed it by yourself.” - Motivation feedback: “You are becoming a strong reader.” <p>6) Guided Reading: During Reading – Comprehension Check</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher opens A Hat and reads slowly, showing pictures clearly.
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none">- The teacher stops at key moments to check understanding.(1) Page: “Pat taps.”- Teacher taps the table to match the action.- Teacher asks, “Who is tapping?”- Student answers; teacher responds: “Yes, Pat is tapping.” (2) Page: “Pat at a map.”- Teacher makes a map shape with hands.- Teacher asks, “What can you see on the map?”- Student responds; teacher says, “Good noticing!” (3) Page: “Pat taps the pot.”- Teacher points to the pot.- Teacher asks, “Why do you think Pat taps the pot?”- Student gives an idea; teacher reinforces: “That is a good guess. You used the picture to help you.”- Teacher keeps tone warm and supportive to build confidence. 7) After Reading – Review & Meaning Link- The teacher closes the book and asks simple review questions: “What did Pat do in the story?” “Where was the map?” - The student answers; teacher affirms the thinking: “Good remembering!” - The teacher and student
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			<p>rebuild the same words from the book: pat, tap, map</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teacher gives motivational feedback: "You read and built all three words. You worked so hard today."
Closure	<p>1) Quick Review</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher and student review the three sounds one more time by matching the pictures of cat, dog, and goat with their beginning sounds /c/, /d/, and /g/. - The student then chooses the sound she feels most confident about and thinks of one more word that begins with that sound (for example, "game" for /g/ or "doll" for /d/). <p>2) Next Step</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher explains what will happen in the next lesson: "Tomorrow we will learn some new sounds. You will hear a popping popcorn sound and a long snake sound." - This prepares the student for /p/, /n/, and /s/ and connects today's learning to the work that is coming next. <p>3) Positive Feedback</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher reinforces the student's effort and role: "You helped me a lot today by fixing the letters I broke on purpose." "You are becoming a real sound detective who looks carefully at both letters and sounds." 	<p>1) Quick Review</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The student reviews the three target sounds by matching /n/, /s/, and /p/ with their picture cards. - She tells the teacher which sound felt easiest today and which one felt hardest. - This short review helps the teacher check her understanding before ending the lesson. <p>2) Next Step</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher says, "Tomorrow we will play a big game with all nine sounds we have learned. You are becoming a real sound detective." - This message prepares the student for the next lesson and builds motivation. <p>3) Positive Feedback</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher gives clear and encouraging feedback: "You used the songs and movements to help you remember the sounds. That was a smart idea." "Your energy helped the lesson stay fun and strong." - This feedback supports confidence and reinforces the strategies that worked well today. 	<p>1) Quick Review</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher and student review the sounds /b/, /m/, and /t/ one more time. - The student says a new word for each sound, using ideas from the story or from her own life. For example, she might say "ball" for /b/ or "mom" for /m/. - The teacher also shows the cover of A Hatagain and asks simple warm-up questions to connect the sounds to reading. "What do you see on the cover?" "Where do we use a map?" - These questions help the student activate meaning before the reading work ends. <p>2) After Reading – Review and Meaning Link</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - After they finish the story, the teacher asks short questions about the pages. "Who is tapping?" "What can you see on the map?" "Why do you think Pat taps the pot?" - These questions also support K.RL.1.1 because they ask her to recall and talk about important details in the story. - The student answers in her own words.

			<p>- Then she builds the three words from the story again using magnetic letters: pat, tap, map. She blends each word and smiles when she finishes.</p> <p>3) Next Step</p> <p>- The teacher explains what will happen next time. “Next time, we will practice more words and use the mirror again so your mouth and ears can tell sounds like /t/ and /d/ apart.”</p> <p>- This prepares the student for the next session and helps her feel ready for the work ahead.</p> <p>4) Positive Feedback</p> <p>- The teacher reinforces her effort and confidence. “You worked so hard today. You listened carefully and used your detective skills.”</p> <p>“You built and read words on your own. I am proud of you.”</p> <p>“You read and built all three words today. You worked so hard.”</p> <p>- The teacher ends with a high-five to close the lesson in a positive way.</p>
<p>Self-Reflection</p>	<p>The student could tell /d/ and /g/ apart fairly well by the end of the lesson, especially when she remembered to check for throat vibration. She was very engaged during the playdough activity and seemed to enjoy fixing the “broken letters.” This multisensory work supported both her focus and her confidence. However, she still showed confusion with /c/,</p>	<p>The student made the /s/ sound very clearly when music and arm movements were used. This shows that multisensory routines continue to support her accuracy. For /p/, she produced the sound well when watching an exaggerated mouth model, but she sometimes mixed /p/ with /b/ when working independently. The /n/ sound had the slowest response</p>	<p>She was engaged during the whole lesson. The Mystery Bag helped her stay focused. She made strong progress with /b/ and /m/. Her biggest growth was with /t/. She used the air cue several times without needing my reminder, which shows increased independence. She still mixes a few lowercase letters, but she</p>

	<p>particularly when it was mixed in with the other two sounds. When the teacher reminded her to touch her throat, her accuracy improved right away. This suggests that the tactile cue is a helpful and necessary strategy for her at this stage.</p> <p>For Day 5, the teacher plans to introduce /p/ and /n/ first because they have clear and visible mouth positions. After that, the teacher will teach /s/ with songs and movement so the lesson does not feel too demanding. After the session, the teacher will also share the phrase “Feel the buzz in your throat” and the ongoing confusion with /c/ with the classroom teacher and ask that the same language be used during the morning routine. This should help reinforce the strategy across settings and give the student more chances to practice.</p>	<p>time and was correct mainly when she used the nose cue. These patterns suggest that she still needs specific and repeated practice with tactile cues.</p> <p>For Day 6, I plan to start with a short warm-up that focuses on /n/ so she can practice it with less support. I will also add one or two chances for independent practice with /p/ to help reduce confusion with /b/. I will continue using music and movement for /s/ because they clearly increased her accuracy. After today’s session, I also plan to share the “nnn plus nose touch” routine with her classroom teacher so the student can practice the same strategy during morning activities. These adjustments support her strengths, address the areas that still need attention, and prepare me for the next steps in the intervention.</p>	<p>corrected herself faster today.</p> <p>When reading CVC words, she blended with more confidence and needed fewer prompts.</p> <p>For the next session, I will add a short lowercase review and give her more chances to compare /t/ and /d/ inside simple words. I will also keep using the mirror because it supports her accuracy and confidence.</p>
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7. Progress-Monitoring Assessment Results

- **Assessment 1:**

- **Date Administered:** September 26, 2025
- **Results:**

1) ANF: 16 letters (baseline 15 → +1)

Zaya could name familiar letters like Band M right away. When she saw a letter she did not know, she waited 2–3 seconds and answered very softly. Sometimes she looked at me before saying the letter, which showed that she was not confident yet. The score change is small, but it shows she is starting to learn how the task works.

2) FSF: 1 point (baseline 0 → +1)

This is still far below the kindergarten goal of 10 points. She could say the first sound /m/ in “man,” but for most words she repeated the whole word. With “map,” she said the word first, stopped for a moment, and then tried /m/. This showed that separating the first sound is still very hard for her.

○ **Observations:**

Zaya was not fully comfortable with the testing situation yet. During ANF, she often looked at my face before answering. This showed worry about being wrong and low confidence. During FSF, she understood that she should say only the first sound, but she has not built a strong strategy for this yet. She often said the whole word first and then checked my reaction. She tried her best, but her performance was not stable.

These early behaviors match her PLAAFP:

- low automaticity with new tasks
- high dependence on the teacher
- slow language processing

This assessment clearly shows why she needs structured, explicit work in early phonics and sound awareness.

• **Assessment 2:**

- **Date Administered:** October 3, 2025
- **Results:**

1) ANF: 21 letters (+5 from Assessment 1)

Zaya has not reached the kindergarten benchmark of 25 letters yet, but she showed clear growth. She could name familiar letters faster and was also able to name some lowercase letters. When she saw an unfamiliar letter, she did not stop or look at the teacher. She paused for a moment and then moved on by herself. This shows that her independence is growing. Her automaticity is still developing, but she is moving in the right direction.

2) FSF: 3 point (+2 from Assessment 1)

The benchmark is 10 points, so there is still a large gap. However, Zaya understood the task better than before and knew she needed to say only the first sound. She gave correct answers for several words, such as /m/ in man, /c/ in cat, and /d/ in dog. She no longer repeated the whole word first and tried to find the

first sound instead. Sometimes she could do this on her own. The skill is not fully stable yet, but the basic idea is beginning to form.

- **Observations:**

The assessment took place at the same small table used in Lesson 2, and Zaya seemed comfortable from the start. In both ANF and FSF, she showed positive changes. When she got stuck, she did not stop or wait for help. She said “hmm...” and tried again on her own. Her response time was still slow, but she stayed focused on the task. In FSF, she sometimes touched her lips or throat to find the first sound. This shows she is trying to use the strategies we practiced in class. She also repeated whole words less often and made more steady attempts to find the first sound. Overall, she showed more “I can try by myself” behavior during this assessment.

These changes match what we saw in her baseline. Zaya originally showed low automaticity, slow processing, and high dependence on the teacher. These traits still appear, but they are becoming weaker. Her ability to pause and try again in ANF, and her beginning success with first-sound isolation in FSF, both show that the intervention is helping her. Her scores are still below the benchmark, but her progress is real and meaningful. Zaya is learning at her own pace, and we can clearly see signs of growth.

- **Assessment 3:**

- **Date Administered:** October 10, 2025
- **Results:**

1) ANF: 22 letters (+1 from Assessment 2)

Zaya named 22 letters this time. The score went up a little from 21. She is still below the benchmark of 25, but her behavior during the task was stronger. She said familiar letters more quickly. When she met a new letter, she did not freeze. She paused for a short moment and then tried on her own. She looked at the teacher much less, and she tried again by herself when she was unsure. Her speed is still slow, but her self-initiated responses were a clear sign of growth.

2) FSF: 4 point (+1 from Assessment 2)

Her score went from 3 to 4. This is still far from the benchmark of 10, but it shows steady progress for this early stage. She answered the first sounds correctly for several words, such as /m/ in man, /d/ in dog, and /g/ in goat. She no longer

repeated the whole word first and tried to say only the first sound with more confidence. The most important change was that she made an attempt on her own before looking for help.

- **Observations:**

Zaya sat down calmly and adjusted to the test right away. In ANF, when she got stuck, she whispered “hmm...” and tried to find the answer herself. She did not stop and wait for the teacher like before. In FSF, she sometimes touched her lips or throat to find the first sound. This shows she was using the strategies from Lessons 5 and 6. She rarely repeated the whole word now. She tried to separate the first sound, and her confidence grew little by little. She also smiled proudly whenever she got a sound correct.

At the beginning of the intervention, Zaya had trouble doing tasks automatically, took longer to process language, and looked to the teacher for help very often. These difficulties are still present, but they are not as strong as before. Her score of 22 letters shows that automaticity is starting to develop. Her FSF score of 4 shows that she is beginning to understand how to isolate the first sound. She also checks the teacher’s face less often and tries more answers on her own. Even though her scores are still below the benchmark, this assessment clearly shows meaningful progress and confirms that the intervention is helping her learn step by step.

- **Assessment 4:**

- **Date Administered:** November 14, 2025
- **Results:**

1) ANF: 25 letters (baseline 15 → +10)

Zaya’s score went from 15 at baseline to 25, which meets the kindergarten goal. She did not get nervous even when the letters were shown quickly. She could name familiar uppercase letters almost right away. She paused a little with lowercase letters, but she was able to keep going on her own after the pause. Right after the three-week break, she forgot a few letters for a moment, but she remembered them quickly during our first review session. After two weeks of review, she became faster, and her letter recognition became more stable.

2) FSF: 6 point (baseline 0 → +6)

There is still a big gap from the benchmark of 10 points, but this is steady progress compared to the baseline, when she could not say even one first sound.

During the assessment, Zaya took her time and said the word slowly to find the first sound. She was able to say the beginning sounds in words like man, sun, and pig on her own. Her speed is still slow, and she stopped longer when the word had a consonant blend or a spelling she did not know. But she clearly understands what the task is now, which is to say only the first sound.

- **Observations:**

When the assessment began, Zaya sat down quietly and understood the task right away. In the ANF part, she paused at a few letters, but she softly said “hmm...” and tried to find the answer by herself. In the FSF task, she touched her lips or made a small sound to figure out the first sound. Before we even started, Zaya proudly said, “I can write my name now,” and she wrote it neatly for me. This was a big moment, because it showed her letter and sound skills were starting to show up in real writing. At baseline, she wrote only the first letter or mixed the order, but now she wrote all the letters in the correct order and checked her work on her own. These changes show that the low automaticity, slow processing, and strong teacher-dependence we saw at baseline are getting weaker. Her ANF score of 25 meets the kindergarten benchmark, and her FSF score of 6 shows steady growth, even though the grade-level goal is still far away. Overall, Zaya now tries first, pauses when she needs to, and keeps going on her own, which matches her PLAAFP and shows that the intervention is helping her change her learning behaviors.

8. Interpretation of Data

- **Data Analysis:**

After ten sessions, Zaya showed steady growth in both naming letters and hearing first sounds. Her baseline scores were ANF 15 and FSF 0, and this showed clear difficulty in both skills. After six sessions she reached ANF 22 and FSF 4, and by the end of session ten she reached ANF 25 and FSF 6.

Her FSF score is still below the kindergarten DIBELS benchmark of 10, but there were meaningful changes that do not show up in the score alone. Zaya started to use the strategies from our lessons during the test. She touched her lips to think about the sound, and she whispered a small sound before answering. This showed that she was moving away from guessing and was beginning to use the strategy on her own. Her learning behavior also changed in a positive way. At first she waited for me because she did not feel confident, but now she tries even when she is not sure. Before the last test she said she could write her name, and she wrote it in the correct order. She looked proud of herself, and this helped her stay focused during the tasks. These emotional changes

supported her learning. She still needs help with FSF accuracy and speed, but she stays engaged when she can use her hands or make sounds. All assessments were given in the same quiet space with the same teacher and the same tools, so the data stayed consistent and fair. Overall, the baseline needs we saw at the start became less strong, and the intervention brought positive academic and emotional growth for Zaya.

- **Graph:**

- a. ANF

- b. FSF

- **New Progress-Monitoring Goal for another 6 weeks:**

After ten sessions, Zaya has shown steady growth in naming letters and hearing first sounds. She now tries problems on her own and uses the strategies we practiced, such as checking her mouth shape or whispering the first sound before answering. Because of this progress, I set her next six-week goals based on both her pace and the expectations in the kindergarten DIBELS benchmarks and the general education curriculum.

Her baseline scores (ANF 15, FSF 0) showed clear difficulty in both skills, but her progress during the intervention was consistent and meaningful. Since she reached ANF 25 and FSF 6 by the final session, it is appropriate to choose goals that she can reach with support while still challenging her. Setting goals in this range will help her continue moving toward the grade-level expectations over time, and her growing confidence shows that she is ready to work toward them.

- Individualized Goal Components

- 1) Condition

- Zaya will complete the DIBELS ANF and FSF tasks in a one-minute test.

- 2) Skill

- ANF: She will name the letters with good accuracy and faster speed.

- FSF: She will say the first sound of a word with clear and correct production.

- 3) Criteria

- ANF: 30 correct letter names.

- FSF: 8 correct first sounds.

- 4) Timeline

- She will work toward these goals over the next six weeks.

- 5) Motivation

- Zaya often says “I can try” when she starts a task. She likes to use the strategies she learned. When she has a clear and short goal, she stays focused and tries her best.

- Rationale for Goal Setting

I first set the FSF goal at 10 because it matched the kindergarten benchmark and because I wanted to encourage strong growth during the short six-session period. Even though her baseline FSF score was 0, I believed she could make quick progress with early support.

After six sessions, Zaya reached ANF 22 and FSF 4. Her ANF increased steadily in a predictable way, while her FSF scores showed that she needed more time to think and did not always use the strategies right away. Based on this pattern, I adjusted the next goals to ANF 30 and FSF 8.

When we returned from the three-week break and completed four review sessions, she reached ANF 25 and FSF 6. This showed that an FSF goal of 8 is still challenging but possible for her.

The updated goals match her learning pace, the DIBELS expectations, the general education curriculum, and the natural steps in reading development from naming letters and hearing first sounds to decoding simple words.

The change in the FSF goal does not mean lowering expectations. It reflects a realistic adjustment based on her developmental stage and her actual growth. It also shows the teacher's professional judgment and the use of data to guide decisions.

9. Impact on Student Learning Reflection

- **Reflection on Learning:**

This ten-session intervention brought meaningful changes to Zaya's early reading skills. Her scores went up, and her confidence grew. She also began to use the strategies we practiced. I tried to watch not only what she got right, but also how she worked and what helped her stay engaged. This reflection helped me understand her learning and my own teaching decisions.

1) Reflection on the student and the learning environment

At the beginning, Zaya had very little confidence. Her baseline scores were ANF 15 and FSF 0. She often looked at me before starting a task. When she felt unsure, she stopped right away. A quiet and predictable one-on-one setting helped her feel safe. The same routine each time lowered her worry. The idea that "it is okay to make mistakes" became the most important support for her.

2) Reflection on the learning goals and intervention

The first goals matched the kindergarten benchmarks. ANF improved quickly. She reached ANF 25 by session ten. FSF grew from 0 to 4 to 6, but the progress slowed in the

middle. The most helpful activities used more than one sense. Zaya checked her mouth shape in a mirror. She practiced a sound quietly before saying it. She tried the sound again until it felt right. These moments showed that she was learning the process, not just the answer. When FSF stayed at 4 for a short time, I realized she needed more time to use the strategies on her own. This helped me adjust the goals later.

3) Reflection on the data and the new goals

The graphs show two clear patterns: ANF went up quickly, and FSF grew slowly but steadily. ANF reached the grade-level line of 25. FSF did not reach 10, but the change from 0 to 6 was still meaningful. Setting the new goals of FSF 8 and ANF 30 felt right. The goals were not lowered. They were based on her real learning pace and how she used the strategies. FSF 8 is challenging but possible. ANF 30 is the next step toward reading with more fluency. The trend lines showed that she could reach these goals with steady practice.

4) Insight on learning and needed adjustments

The biggest insight was that Zaya's learning grew when her confidence grew. When she wrote her name and said, "I can try," I saw a real shift. This showed she was ready to take more ownership of her learning.

For the next steps, I plan to give more short timed practice for FSF. I will also add simple syllable activities to help her move toward reading CVC words. If she does not reach FSF 8 in six weeks, I will change the amount or type of support instead of lowering the goal. I may also check her phonological skills more closely.

5) Reflection on my professional growth

This experience helped me grow as a teacher. I learned that progress monitoring is not just collecting scores. It guides my teaching decisions.

I noticed areas where I need to improve. I want to plan better activities for skills that take longer to master, like FSF. I also want to give the right help when a student cannot use a strategy right away. I hope to read learning patterns more clearly, even from small changes. To support my growth, I will use Beginning Reading resources from the What Works Clearinghouse. I will join Heggerty trainings to strengthen my routines. I plan to review DIBELS modules to read trend lines more accurately. I will also study more from Reading Rockets and LETRS.

This intervention helped Zaya grow in her skills and her confidence. It also reminded me that looking at student data is more than checking scores. The data helps me decide what

to teach next and how to support the student. I want to use what I learned here to make better choices in my future lessons with her.

10. Reports to Teacher and Parent/Guardian:

- **Teacher Report:**

1) Student Strengths and Initial Observations

During the ten sessions, I learned many things about how Zaya learns. She showed several strong qualities:

- a. She tries again when she is encouraged, even if she hesitates at first.
- b. She watches the teacher's mouth and gestures carefully and copies them well.
- c. She stays focused when she can touch or move things, such as clay, picture cards, or a sand tray.
- d. She joins activities more quickly when they include rhythm or songs.
- e. She works well in one-on-one time and keeps a positive relationship with the teacher.

These strengths helped me plan lessons that fit her learning style.

2) Baseline Data and Initial Goals

At the beginning, Zaya's scores showed that she needed strong support in early reading skills.

Skill	Baseline	Benchmark	Level
ANF (Alphabet Naming Fluency)	15	25	Well Below Benchmark
FSF (First Sound Fluency)	0	10	Well Below Benchmark

Initial Goals:

- a. ANF: Move from 15 → 25 (benchmark)
- b. FSF: Move from 0 → 10 (benchmark)

Both skills are essential for kindergarten-level reading readiness, so she needed a structured plan.

3) Chosen Intervention and Why

I chose a Structured Literacy approach with multisensory phonics because this method is clear, step-by-step, and helps students who struggle with phonological awareness and letter automaticity.

Research supports this approach:

- Moats (2020): Explicit and systematic instruction helps young readers.
- National Reading Panel (2000): Phonemic awareness and phonics instruction improve early reading.

Zaya's baseline showed she was at the earliest stage of both skills, so this plan matched her needs well.

4) What We Did in the Intervention

The intervention used these core ideas:

- a. Explicit instruction (clear modeling)
- b. Systematic steps
- c. Cumulative review
- d. Multisensory activities

(1) Activities Used

a. Letter Sets: b-c-d → m-n-s → t-p-g

b. Explicit Practice

- I modeled the sound, and she repeated it.
- She traced letters in sand or with her finger.
- She matched letters with pictures.
- She watched mouth shapes to understand how sounds are made.

c. Multisensory Activities

- Sand tray writing
- "Letter Café" pretend play
- Rhythm shaker activities
- Sound Detective game

d. Phonological Awareness (FSF)

- Sorting pictures by first sound
- Clapping when the target sound was heard
- Choosing the correct beginning sound card

e. Automaticity

- Short timed naming practice at the end of sessions

f. Adaptations Based on Zaya's Needs

- Kept activities short (3–5 minutes)
- Added more visual cues
- Limited the number of letters at one time
- Gave easier tasks when she looked overwhelmed

5) Student Progress and Data Review

Skill	Baseline	Assessment 1	Assessment 2	Assessment 3	Assessment 4	Benchmark	Growth
ANF	15	16	21	22	25	25	+10
FSF	0	1	3	4	6	10	+6

How to Understand This Growth

- ANF: She reached the benchmark.
- FSF: She did not reach the benchmark yet, but moving from 0 → 6 is strong growth.

6) Important Qualitative Growth (Beyond the Score)

In the second half of the intervention, Zaya began using strategies on her own, without being told. She:

- Lightly touched her lips to think about the sound
- Whispered the first sound before saying the answer
- Checked her mouth shape in a mirror to self-correct

These behaviors show she is internalizing the skills, which is a key step toward independent reading.

7) New Intra-Individual Goals

Based on her progress trend, I set new goals that match her learning pace.

- ANF: 30 → to build fluency, not just accuracy
- FSF: 8 → challenging but realistic for the next phase

These goals are not “lowered expectations”; they reflect her own growth line and are aligned with how she learns best.

8) Adjusted Intervention Plan (Next Steps)

To help her reach the new goals, I will adjust the plan as follows:

o Planned Adjustments

- a. Add minimal pairs for clearer sound contrast
- b. Continue mouth-shape practice and articulatory cues
- c. Increase short FSF timed practice
- d. Strengthen letter–sound connections
- e. Use more clay, sand, and rhythm activities because they fit her strengths

9) Advocacy for Continued Services

Zaya still needs structured support because:

- a. FSF is a foundational skill for CVC word reading
- b. She learns best with short, hands-on, guided practice
- c. Her home environment (many siblings, parent work hours) may make consistent practice challenging

o Recommendation:

→ Continue small-group or one-on-one intervention 2–3 times a week to maintain momentum and help her reach the new goals.

• Parent Report for Zaya

Hello. My name is Kyoungun Song. I am a graduate student in education at Indiana State University, and I have been working with Zaya to help her grow in early reading skills. As part of my training, I worked with her in ten one on one reading sessions to support her alphabet naming and first sound skills.

In this report, I want to share what Zaya practiced during our sessions and how she grew during this time. I also included a few simple ways you can support her at home without extra work or stress. Zaya always came to every session with a good attitude. Her strong learning habits helped her make steady progress, and it was wonderful to see her confidence grow each week.

1) Zaya's Strengths and Positive Changes

During the ten sessions, I saw many strengths in Zaya.

- a. She tries again when someone encourages her. Even if she hesitates at first, she tries once more when I say try again.
- b. She watches my mouth and hand motions carefully and copies them very well. This helps her learn new sounds.
- c. She stays focused when she can touch or move things like clay, picture cards or a sand tray.
- d. She joins activities quickly when they include rhythm or songs. She enjoys sound play when it feels like music.
- e. She learns well in one on one time and keeps a warm and positive relationship with the teacher.

Zaya’s strengths helped her learn in a happy and confident way.

How these strengths help at home: Zaya learns best when she can touch things, move her hands, hear rhythm and songs, follow mouth shapes and receive warm praise. These ideas are the most helpful ways to support her at home.

2) Zaya’s Progress

Before looking at the scores, here is a short explanation of the two skills:

- a. ANF (Alphabet Naming Fluency) means how quickly and correctly a child can say the names of letters. This is important because children who can name letters easily learn sounds and reading more smoothly.
- b. FSF (First Sound Fluency) means how well a child can hear the first sound in a word. This is a key kindergarten skill because it helps children get ready for sounding out simple words.

Here is a simple chart of her progress:

Skill	Start Score	Final Score	Kindergarten Goal
ANF (Alphabet Naming Fluency)	15	25	25
FSF (First Sound Fluency)	0	6	10

What this means:

- a. Zaya reached the kindergarten goal in ANF.
- b. She did not reach the FSF goal yet, but moving from 0 to 6 shows strong and meaningful growth.

This growth also shows that she is beginning to notice sounds in words, which is an important early reading step.

3) New Learning Goals

After completing the six-session intervention and reviewing Zaya's progress, I created new goals that better match her learning pace and the kindergarten reading expectations.

a. ANF goal: 30

b. FSF goal: 8

I chose these goals based on two things:

a. Her growth so far – she showed clear improvement and is beginning to use helpful reading strategies on her own

b. What is developmentally appropriate for her age – these goals are realistic for kindergarten learners and help her continue building strong early reading skills.

These goals are challenging but still reachable for Zaya, and they help guide what we will focus on in the next step of her learning.

4) Next Steps at School

Zaya learns well with short and clear activities. She would benefit from:

a. Two or three short sound lessons each week

b. Hands on activities

c. Frequent review

d. One on one or small group lessons

These supports match the way she learns best.

5) Simple Ways to Help at Home

I know your time is limited. These activities take one minute and can be done during daily routines. Please keep them fun, not like homework.

a. First Sound Hunt

You can choose objects that Zaya likes such as a bear, ball or bag and say something like Bear begins with the b sound. You can also walk around the house together and ask What things start with the b sound to make it fun. Zaya likes touching things while she learns, so it helps if she holds the items herself. If she has older or younger siblings nearby, they can join the game by finding objects that start with the same sound, which makes the activity even more fun and active.

b. Mouth Shape Practice

You can say sounds like b j k while showing your mouth slowly and clearly, then ask Zaya to copy your mouth shape. She enjoys looking in a mirror during this activity, and siblings can join by taking turns making a sound and having everyone copy it. Kids often enjoy this because it feels like a silly face game rather than a study activity.

c. Rhythm and Sound Play

You can clap and say s s sun or sing groups of words with the same beginning sound such as banana bag beach. Zaya reacts very well to rhythm, and this becomes even more fun when siblings join in as a small “sound band,” taking turns clapping or choosing the next sound. It keeps the activity short, lively and easy for everyone.

d. Touch and Learn Activities

Zaya can make letters with clay, write first letters in a sand tray or group fridge letter magnets by beginning sound. These activities match her learning style because she likes to touch and move things. If siblings join, each child can pick one letter or sound and build something with it, turning the activity into a shared play time rather than extra work for one child.

e. Praise Time

Zaya learns best with warm and gentle support. Short praise helps her focus and try again, even when a task feels hard. Simple phrases like I like how you tried again, I like how you looked at your mouth shape, or Your effort is more important than being right make a big difference. These phrases work well with siblings too, turning the moment into a positive family interaction rather than a test or correction.

Your family schedule is very busy, and it may be hard to set aside long study time. The good news is that Zaya grows well with short and simple moments during the day. You can help her by adding small sound activities into your daily life, such as noticing first sounds during play or while getting ready. These activities take less than one minute and do not feel like work. The most important part is keeping the moments light and positive so she stays confident and willing to try. Small steps like these make a big difference over time.

6) Helpful Learning Resources for Zaya

a. Local Resources in Terre Haute

Place	Program or Area	Why It Helps Zaya
Vigo County Public Library https://vigolibrary.org/	Story Time (Runs twice a month, registration required)	The teacher reads a picture book and leads hands-on activities such as clay work, block play, movement mats, and

		simple music. These multisensory activities match how Zaya learns best.
Terre Haute Children’s Museum https://terrehautechildrensmuseum.com/	Sound and Movement area	Zaya learns well when she can move her body, follow rhythm, and explore through touch. This area fits her learning strengths.

b. Online Learning Resources

Website	What It Offers	Link
Reading Rockets – Early Literacy Games	Simple reading games you can try at home.	https://www.readingrockets.org/reading-games
Heggerty – Family Support Videos	Videos that show mouth shapes and early sound practice.	https://heggerty.org/family-resources/
Starfall – Early Reading Games	Letter–sound games and early reading practice.	https://www.starfall.com

7) Final Message

Zaya made wonderful progress during our sessions. She grew in her skills and her confidence. The way she tries again and uses strategies by herself shows that she is ready for the next steps in reading.

Your small words of encouragement help her more than you may realize. I look forward to continuing to support her growth at school. Please contact me anytime if you have questions. I am always cheering for Zaya.

With warm regards

Kyoungeun Song

11. Video Recording-Self Evaluation Form

	Time in Video	Example from Video – could be quote and description	Self-Evaluation: refer to the criteria
1. Stated Goal	1:31	<p>At the beginning of the lesson, I gave the student a playful role as the “Sound Detective” and said, “Today we’ll practice our special sounds: /b/, /m/, and /t/, and then we’ll put those sounds together to read real words.”</p> <p>This one sentence clearly explained the sequence of the lesson: reviewing sounds, blending words, and then reading the decodable book A Hat. The rest of the lesson followed this plan exactly. We used magnetic letters to match sounds to letters, practiced reading words such as pat, tap, and map, and ended by reading the text. All parts of the lesson aligned with the introduction so the student could follow the flow easily.</p>	<p>At the beginning of the lesson, I explained the steps in a clear order: reviewing the sounds, reading words, and then reading the text. This helped the student understand the plan for the day and how each part connected. She entered the lesson already knowing, “We will practice /b/, /m/, and /t/, then blend the sounds to read real words, and finally read a book.” Sharing the goal and the order in one simple sentence made it easier for her to stay focused. She did not lose track of why each activity mattered, which helped her move through the lesson with more confidence. Using the phrase “Sound Detective” also made the introduction feel more playful and motivating.</p> <p>For future lessons, I want to keep this clear structure because it supported her understanding and engagement. However, I also want to check if she can repeat the plan back to me in her own words to confirm her understanding of each step. If needed, I can also add a quick visual schedule or ask her to point to each step as we move through the lesson so she can</p>

			follow the sequence more independently.
2. Stated Why	1:40	<p>In the introduction, I explained why blending sounds is important by saying, “When you can blend sounds, you can read new books all by yourself.”</p> <p>With this sentence, I clearly showed how this skill is connected to reading independently.</p> <p>This sentence helped the student understand that today’s skill is not just a simple task, but a key ability that helps you read new books on your own. I explained this idea in a way that matched the student’s level.</p> <p>In other words, I connected the need for this skill to the student’s long-term reading development.</p>	<p>This explanation used simple but clear language that fit the student’s level, and it was effective in telling her exactly why she needed to learn this skill.</p> <p>This explanation also showed the student how the skill would connect to real reading later on. Because of that, the activities that followed (reviewing sounds, reading words, and reading the text) felt more meaningful for her.</p> <p>Another important point in reading instruction is “connecting the skill to a purpose so the student feels more motivated,” and I was able to do that naturally in this lesson.</p> <p>Because of this, the student participated actively and understood that her effort would help her become a stronger reader.</p>
3. Modeled Steps <i>Criteria –</i>	2:05	<p>During the modeling part of the lesson, I showed the sounds b, m, and tin order and explained each one clearly.</p> <p>For b, I said, “Lips together and then pop open.”</p> <p>For m, I said, “Lips closed, air through the nose.”</p> <p>For t, I said, “Tongue behind your teeth, little air coming out.”</p> <p>When I explained /t/, I first made the wrong sound /d/on purpose and said, “There was no air. That was /d/. Let me try again—/t/.”</p>	<p>In this part of the lesson, I kept a clear and easy-to-follow sequence, moving from b to m to tin a way that matched how the mouth changes when making each sound.</p> <p>The modeling also included important teaching practices such as:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> showing the correct articulation with my mouth, using visual, auditory, and tactile

		<p>This helped the student see how I fixed my mistake and understand my thinking process.</p> <p>At the end, I used a small mirror so the student could look at her own mouth and check her articulation.</p>	<p>cues together,</p> <p>c. giving only the key information without extra technical words,</p> <p>d. thinking aloud so the student could hear how I solved the problem.</p> <p>A strong moment was when the student later made a mistake with the /t/sound and then put her hand in front of her mouth to check for air. This showed that the tactile cue from the modeling became her own self-correction strategy, which is exactly what I hoped would happen.</p> <p>Because of this, I felt that the way I modeled the sound–letter connections supported her accurate pronunciation and helped her read the target words more confidently.</p>
4. Independent Practice	5:38	<p>During this part of the lesson, the student made the words pat → tap → map by herself using magnetic letters.</p> <p>She pointed to each letter and blended the sounds to read each word. After that, she read the decodable text A Hat, which helped her use her word-reading skills in sentences and a simple story. I gave only small hints when needed so she could feel successful on her own.</p>	<p>In this independent practice, I planned the activities so the student could see how her letter–sound skills connect to real word reading.</p> <p>Having her build the words on her own strengthened the link between sounds and letters, and it also helped her understand that changing just the first sound creates a new word.</p> <p>Moving directly from word reading to a decodable text allowed her to apply the skill right away, which is an important part of early literacy instruction. While reading the text, she also showed understanding by</p>

			<p>connecting the words to actions and meaning in the story.</p> <p>Overall, this part of the lesson gave her enough practice, helped her apply the skill in a real reading situation, and let her experience success. I also saw her use her finger to track the words more smoothly. When she was unsure, she reread the line by herself, and this showed that she was starting to use the decoding strategy on her own. These steps supported her confidence and helped her see that she could read on her own.</p>
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Reflection on Explicit Lesson

1) What did I do well?

In this lesson, I organized the flow in a clear way:

reviewing sounds → building words → reading the text.

The activities connected well, and the student could see how each step supported the next one. The air/no-air tactile cue for /t/ and /d/ was especially helpful. Later in the lesson, the student used this strategy on her own and corrected her mistake without my prompt. This showed that the modeling was not just a demonstration but a strategy she truly learned and used independently. Seeing her use the cue by herself was a very positive change. During word reading, I also connected word meaning to actions, like having her tap while reading “tap.” This helped her understand the meaning of the word and improved her accuracy at the same time.

2) What would I like to improve next time?

First, the student still had trouble telling apart lowercase t and d visually. In the next lesson, I want to add a short lowercase automaticity warm-up to help her build faster and stronger letter–sound connections.

Second, during the guided reading part, I asked, “Why do you think Pat taps the pot?”, but I did not give her enough wait time before moving on. Because of this, she did not have enough space to think and share her idea.

Next time, I want to be more intentional about giving her time to think. I plan to give her more time to think before she answers. I also want to use simple routines, like asking the question, pausing, and then asking again if needed. When I ask meaning-based questions, I will slow down a little so she has enough time to share her ideas.

12. Collaboration Log

Date/Time	Participants	Reason/Problem	Problem-Solving Step	Activity	Notes from Meeting
18 50- 20 min.)	Host teacher and the interventionist (myself)	A, S	2	Met with the host teacher to review the student's background and discuss reading observations. Agreed to begin the intervention with simple routines and sound-focused, play-based activities.	The classroom teacher explained the student's home background and learning habits. At home, the mother is very busy, so the student does not get much help with schoolwork. At school, she is quiet and shy, and she does not raise her hand or speak loudly on her own. However, she gets along well with her classmates and joins play-based activities with good energy. The teacher also said that the student opens up to new adults quickly, so she thinks the one-on-one time will help the student feel safe and ready to learn. I shared what I saw in today's reading lesson. The student followed the print with her eyes, but she did not respond right away when she heard the first sound. She often looked at her classmates' mouths to copy them. When she met a new word, she stopped and looked for a picture or other visual clues. These behaviors showed that her phonemic awareness is still weak and that she needs more support with hearing and telling sounds apart. Based on this information, we agreed to begin with simple and predictable routines. We decided to use activities that focus on hearing and saying sounds, and to

					include movement and playful tasks. We also agreed not to add too many new skills at first. Our goal for the early sessions is to build her confidence through repetition and small successes. This became the first plan for the case study.
19 50- 20 min.)	Host teacher, Reading Specialist, and the interventionist (myself)	A, S	3	Met with the host teacher and Reading Specialist to review the baseline results. Agreed to begin the intervention with a multi-sensory phonics approach and approved 1:1 pull-out sessions during class.	I shared what I saw in the baseline assessment. The student is very motivated, but she has almost no connection between sounds and letters. The reading specialist said the student learns better when she can see and move, not just listen and repeat. The classroom teacher shared the class averages and said the student is below the group. But she also said the student learns faster when she feels active and involved. I shared my plan for the first six sessions. We will focus on sounds, mouth movements, and blending. The reading specialist suggested using a multi-sensory phonics approach. The teacher said I could take the student to the hallway for 1:1 lessons if needed. She said it was fine to step out during class time.
25 50- 20 min.)	Host teacher and the interventionist (myself)	A, S	4	Discussed the student's confusion with /t/ and the need for a quieter setting. Planned to use the library corner for upcoming sessions and to add simple tactile cues to support clearer sound	I talked with the teacher about what I noticed in the lesson. The student learned /b/ and /m/ quickly, but she was still confused about /t/. I explained that she might need a simple tactile cue, like feeling the air in front of her mouth, and that I will model the sound more clearly next time. I also brought up that the

				production.	hallway was very noisy during the lesson, and the student lost focus several times. The teacher said that the learning environment can affect the student a lot, especially in the early sessions, so she needs a quiet space. She agreed that the hallway noise could make it harder for the student to stay focused. She suggested a small corner in the library, saying it would be much quieter and help the student stay calm. She told me I can use that space for future lessons.
26 50- 20 min.)	Host teacher and the interventionist (myself)	A	2	Discussed the student's slow response to /t/ and her strong engagement during role-play. Planned to use the prompt-pause-re-ask routine and to include more play-based activities to support confidence and motivation.	I shared that the student still took a long time to respond to the /t/ sound. She remembered /m/ and /b/ well and tried them on her own. She was not confident with /t/. I also said that she showed good participation when we did the role-play activity. The teacher said that the student also likes play-based activities in the classroom. She often waits for her classmates to answer first. The teacher told me that this student needs enough wait time before she speaks. She suggested using the prompt-pause-re-ask routine. We decided to try this routine in the next sessions. We also agreed to use more role-play activities because they help the student stay motivated.
1 50- 20 min.)	Host teacher and the interventionist (myself)	A	4	Discussed the student's confusion between /c/ and /d/ and her strong focus during the music	I mentioned to the teacher that the student kept mixing up the /c/ and /d/ sounds. The teacher said that she often sees the same thing in the classroom. During read-aloud

				<p>activity. Decided to use short rhythms and chants in future lessons to help her hear and remember the sound differences.</p>	<p>time, the student sometimes stops or asks again because she cannot tell the two sounds apart. I also explained that the student focused much better during the music activity with drums and shakers. She followed the rhythm and joined the activity with good energy. We both agreed that the student responds well to music and play-based activities. We talked about adding short rhythms or chants to help her learn the sounds. For example, “D, D, D has a voice. C, C, C is a quiet air sound.” A simple pattern like this may help her remember the difference. We decided to keep using this rhythm-based approach in the next sessions.</p>
/3 50- 20 min.)	Host teacher and the interventionist (myself)	A	4	<p>Reviewed the student’s strong engagement with hands-on letter work and noted her ability to self-correct. Planned to continue tactile letter-building tasks and reinforce sound–shape connections in upcoming sessions.</p>	<p>I told the teacher that the student fixed her own mistakes while making letters with playdough. She checked the shapes again and corrected them on her own. The teacher said that this student enjoys hands-on activities and that this way of learning works well for her. We agreed that tactile activities help her remember the sounds and tell them apart. We decided to keep using activities where she can make or move the letters. We will also keep working on connecting each sound with the letter shape.</p>
/9 50- 20	Host teacher and the interventionist (myself)	A	4	<p>Talked with the host teacher about the student’s progress with</p>	<p>I said that the student learns the /s/ sound quickly, but the /n/ sound is still hard for her. The teacher said that the student needs</p>

<p>) .)</p>				<p>the /s/ and /n/ sounds and the need to begin each lesson with easier sounds to build confidence. Noted the student's growing excitement about school and planned a "success first, challenge later" structure for the next session.</p>	<p>to start with sounds she already knows well. This helps her feel confident. She suggested beginning with easy sounds and moving to harder ones in the next session. The teacher also shared that the student is more excited to come to school now. In the morning, she asks, "Is the teacher coming today?" She said that the parent also noticed changes at home. The student tries to write her name and sometimes asks how to read signs when they go out. We both felt that this emotional comfort and excitement is helping her learn. We decided that the next session should follow a "success first, challenge later" plan so she can stay confident and motivated.</p>
<p>10 50- 20 in.)</p>	<p>Host teacher and the interventionist (myself)</p>	<p>A</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>Reviewed the student's progress scores with the host teacher and discussed the need for a three-week pause to check skill retention. Set new goals for lowercase automaticity, reaching FSF 8, and using self-correction in short texts. Planned review lessons after the break to support steady growth.</p>	<p>I talked about the student's scores (ANF 22, FSF 4) and said that she showed good growth over the last three weeks. The teacher said she has also seen the student try to make sounds on her own during class. I said the growth is positive, but we need a short break to see if she can keep the skills. Because of this, we decided to pause after six sessions, observe for three weeks, and then do review lessons. This will help us see how well she can keep and use what she learned. For the next goals, we agreed to work on lowercase automaticity, reaching FSF 8, and using self-correction during short text reading. The teacher said the student often stops or gets confused when reading</p>

					<p>lowercase letters, so building this skill may help her read faster and feel more confident. For FSF, the teacher said she still needs a little more time to think, but she may reach 8 with steady practice. The student already tries to fix her own mistakes in single words, so moving this to short texts seems like the right next step. The teacher also said the student's mood and participation are more stable now, which should support her learning.</p>
<p>/6 50- 20 min.)</p>	<p>Host teacher and the interventionist (myself)</p>	<p>A</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>Reviewed the student's hesitation and slower blending after the break. Discussed similar observations from classroom reading. Agreed to pause new skills and use the next four sessions for review and confidence-building practice to strengthen sounds and blending.</p>	<p>I shared that the student hesitated a lot when reading words she had already learned. Her blending was also slower than before. I noticed that even familiar words made her stop for a moment, and she sometimes looked at me to check before saying the word. The teacher said she saw the same thing in class. During read-aloud time, the student paused at words like "nap" and "pen" and took extra time to think.</p> <p>The teacher explained that a backward slide after a break is normal. She said it is better to focus on review and steady practice instead of adding new skills right now. I agreed with her. For phase two, we decided not to introduce new interventions and to use the next four sessions to review and strengthen what we taught in the first six sessions. Our goal for this stage is to help the student rebuild her confidence with the sounds and improve her blending</p>

/7 50- 20 min.)	Host teacher and the interventionist (myself)	A	4	Reviewed the teacher's observations of the student showing renewed confidence and trying sounds independently. Discussed the positive emotional impact of the one-on-one sessions and agreed to continue the review phase while ensuring a clear success moment in each lesson to support confidence and motivation.	again. The teacher told me that the student showed more confidence during reading time yesterday. She tried the sounds again, even the ones that were hard before, and said, "I know this sound." The teacher said it looked like she was starting to remember things again. The teacher also shared that the student waited for me a lot during the three-week break. When I came back yesterday, she was very happy to have the lesson again. The teacher said that our one-on-one time seems to help her not only with literacy but also with her emotional comfort, and she thanked me for that. We agreed to continue the review sessions and to make sure the student has a clear moment of success in each lesson to keep her confidence and motivation strong.
13 50- 20 min.)	Host teacher, Reading Specialist, and the interventionist (myself)	A	4	Noted the student's growing independence with phonics strategies, such as using airflow checks for /t/, whispering first sounds, and adjusting her mouth shape with the mirror. The host teacher shared similar observations from class, showing that the strategies are becoming part of the student's	What I noticed today was that the student checked the /t/ sound by placing her hand in front of her mouth to feel the air. She also whispered the first sound for /p/ before saying the word. When she read a new word, she looked in the mirror and tried to fix her mouth shape. These actions showed that she is starting to use the strategies on her own. The teacher said she saw similar behavior in the classroom. During read-aloud time, the student paused at words like "top" and "pig," touched her mouth, or quietly said

				<p>routine. We planned to move into more text-level decoding in the final session so she can apply these self-check strategies while reading sentences.</p>	<p>the first sound before reading the rest. We agreed that this means the strategies are becoming more natural for her. For the final session, we decided to add more text-level decoding and support her so she can use these self-check strategies while reading sentences.</p>
14 50- 20 min.)	Host teacher, Reading Specialist, and the interventionist (myself)	A	4	<p>Reviewed the student's final scores with the team and noted steady growth. Observed her reading "A Hat" and using blending strategies with confidence. The host teacher and Reading Specialist shared similar progress in class and emphasized the need for continued phonemic awareness and decodable text practice. Agreed to continue short, clear tasks and hands-on review to support ongoing growth.</p>	<p>I reviewed the student's final scores (ANF 25, FSF 6) and explained that she showed steady growth. For our last activity, we read the decodable book "A Hat." She blended the sounds in hat and pot on her own and said, "I can read this!" with confidence.</p> <p>The classroom teacher shared that the student is now more involved in class and tries first sounds by herself. We agreed that these behaviors show she is beginning to use the strategies independently. I also said that short, clear tasks, hands-on activities, frequent review, and small-group or one-on-one lessons will continue to help her. The teacher agreed and said she will adjust class work in that direction. The Reading Specialist added that the student still needs steady practice with phonemic awareness and decodable texts. We ended by agreeing to work together to support her growth in a stable learning environment.</p>

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